

CONSUMER AND RETAILER PERCEPTION ABOUT MAJOR PATANJALI FOOD PRODUCTS IN NAGPUR CITY

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Abstract

This research examines consumer and retailer perceptions of Patanjali food products in Nagpur, focusing on economic viability and factors influencing buying behavior. Through surveys and interviews, the study explores key elements such as price, quality, and brand reputation, alongside challenges like product availability and accessibility. Patanjali's marketing, which emphasizes spiritual and Ayurvedic values, has contributed to customer loyalty and retailer satisfaction. The findings reveal that Patanjali products are particularly popular among middle-aged, educated men with moderate incomes. Cow Ghee and Honey are the most preferred products, while items like Noodles have seen less success. Television advertisements have been effective, though brand loyalty remains moderate, with many consumers uncertain about future purchases. Opinions on pricing and availability are mixed, with some finding the products overpriced or inconsistently stocked. While trust in the brand is generally strong, concerns regarding product safety and quality influence consumer loyalty. The research concludes that addressing these concerns is essential for maintaining credibility and improving consumer retention. By enhancing product quality and engaging more effectively with customers, Patanjali can strengthen its market position and appeal to a broader range of consumers.

Keywords: Patanjali, Food Product, Consumer, Perception, Satisfaction, Quality

Introduction

In recent years, the way we look at food around the world has changed a lot. This is because of new technologies, how our lifestyles are changing, and because more people care about being healthy and taking care of the planet. People aren't just eating whatever is given to them; they are actively looking for information, checking labels, and forming opinions about their food. This shift has made it really important for businesses to understand what people want in their food so they can meet the changing needs and preferences of consumers. Patanjali is a brand that became very successful quickly, even when big companies in the food industry were facing challenges. The study looks at why Patanjali succeeded, especially in the food sector, where they mixed traditional knowledge with modern preferences. It focuses on what people and stores think about Patanjali's food products to understand why they became so popular.

Need and importance of the study

This study on consumer perception of Patanjali food products is important due to the brand's rapid growth in India's FMCG sector. Understanding what drives consumer choices helps shape marketing strategies and shows how Patanjali compares to competitors. The brand's focus on Ayurveda and Indian traditions influences consumer views, especially with rising interest in health and natural products. Economically, the research highlights Patanjali's impact on markets, guiding marketing, product development, and business strategies. It also improves our understanding of how cultural factors shape consumer behavior and brand perception, paving the way for further research.

Objectives of study

To identify the demographic traits of consumers and retailers of selected Patanjali food products.

To study the variables influencing consumers and retailers perception of Patanjali food products

To identify the constraints faced by consumers and retailers of major food products.

Methodology**Area of study**

Present study was conducted in four regions (east, west, north, south) of Nagpur city.

Period of study

The data was collected for year 2023-2024.

Source of data

The primary data was collected through the personal interview of 50 consumers and 5 retailers through structured questionnaire.

Analytical tools

NAAS Rating – 04.17

To accomplish objective of study the simple tabular analysis was used along with the percentage analysis and graphical representation.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 the demographic profile of the consumers shows that most are middle-aged, with a significant portion of younger and fewer older individuals. The consumer base is predominantly male. Family sizes are generally moderate, with most households having four to five members. Educational attainment varies, with a large segment holding degrees, followed by those with school-level education and a smaller group of postgraduates. In terms of occupation, consumers are primarily employed, with notable segments involved in business, homemaking, and studies.

Table 2 data reveals that the majority of consumers fall within the middle-income range, with a significant portion earning moderate annual household incomes. A smaller percentage of consumers belong to the lower income brackets, while the higher income groups comprise a comparatively smaller but notable share. This distribution highlights a diverse consumer base with varying financial capabilities, predominantly concentrated around middle-income levels.

Table 3 data highlights the consumption patterns of various products among consumers. Cow ghee is the most popular, followed closely by honey and edible oil. Pulses and juices are also commonly consumed, reflecting a preference for staple and health-related items. Other frequently purchased products include atta, spices, and chyawanprash. Biscuits and noodles are less commonly consumed, indicating a lower preference among the surveyed consumers.

Table 4 data indicates that television and social media are the dominant sources of information for consumers, serving as the most influential media channels. Recommendations from friends also play a notable role, albeit to a lesser extent. In-store promotions, online advertisements, and the Patanjali website are among the least influential, suggesting that direct marketing efforts and official brand channels have a comparatively minor impact on consumer behavior.

Table 5 data shows that retailers are generally satisfied with the supply and consistency of availability of food products, with these factors receiving the highest satisfaction levels. Retailers also view the level of demand positively, though a few remain neutral. The rate of profit margin and overall profitability, however, tend to receive more neutral feedback, indicating moderate satisfaction among retailers. Overall, supply consistency stands out as a key strength, while profit margins present areas of potential improvement.

Table 6 data reveals varying levels of consumer satisfaction across different factors. Consumers are highly satisfied with the quantity, availability, and taste of the products, which received the highest

satisfaction rankings. Factors such as effectiveness, price, and packaging also garnered positive responses but with a mix of neutral and slightly dissatisfied feedback. The lowest satisfaction levels were observed in factors like price and packaging, with some consumers expressing dissatisfaction, albeit in smaller numbers. Overall, quantity and availability emerged as the top-rated factors, reflecting their importance to consumers.

Table 7 shows that consumers are mostly satisfied but have mixed feelings about recommending the products to others and continuing their use. Many feel some products are expensive, and ads play a big role in their choices. While natural ingredients are acknowledged, Patanjali products are not always the top choice for many consumers.

Table 8 data shows that Patanjali food products are generally easy to find, though availability can vary by location. Most consumers find the pricing somewhat affordable, but some feel it is still a bit high compared to other brands. Trust in the brand's safety and reliability is strong, although some consumers have minor concerns. Satisfaction is generally high, with most consumers rarely facing issues, but occasional problems do occur. The brand image significantly influences many consumers' buying decisions, although for some, it has little impact on their choices.

Conclusion

Patanjali products are popular among middle-aged, educated males, especially working professionals and business owners who value health.

Cow Ghee and Honey are the most favored products, while Noodles are less popular, showing varying success across product categories. Television ads are the most effective, but there's potential to improve consumer engagement and loyalty as many remain neutral about repurchasing.

Products are generally accessible, though availability varies by location, and opinions on pricing are mixed, with some finding them expensive.

Trust in Patanjali is strong, but some consumers have safety concerns, and brand loyalty is moderate, with mixed willingness to recommend the brand.

The brand image significantly influences purchasing decisions for many, but less so for some, suggesting a need for stronger brand differentiation.

Retailers are satisfied with supply and demand; products are reliably available, but profit margins could be better for some.

Improvement areas include product quality, pricing, availability consistency, and enhancing engagement and loyalty, especially among younger consumers.

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Table 1: Demographic traits of the consumers

Age	Consumers	Percentage	Gender	Consumers	Percentage
Up to 30 years	14	28	Male	36	72
31 to 50 years	30	60	Female	14	28
Above 50 years	06	12	Family size		
Educational qualification			Up to 3	16	32
			4 to 5	32	64
			Above 5	02	04
School Level	14	28	Occupation		
Degree	24	48	Student	05	10
PG	10	20	House Wife	09	18
Professional	02	04	Employed	25	50
			Business	11	22
Total	50	100	Total	50	100

Table 2: Distribution of on the basis of household income

Sr. No	Household annual income	Consumers	Percentage
1	Up to Rs 2,00,000L	05	10
2	Rs.2,00,001L to Rs.4,00,000L	08	16
3	Rs.4,00,001L to Rs.6,00,000L	15	30
4	Rs.6,00,001L to Rs.8,00,000L	12	24
5	Rs.8,00,000L to 10,00,000L	06	12
6	Above Rs 10,00,000L	04	08

Table 3: Consumption of selected food product in Nagpur city

Sr. No	Product name	Consumers	Percentage
1	Cow ghee	27	54
2	Honey	23	46

3	Edible oil	20	40
4	Pulses	21	42
5	Juices	16	32
6	Atta	14	28
7	Spices	17	34
8	Chyawanprash	17	34
9	Biscuits	15	30
10	Noodles	08	16

Table 4: Consumers influences for consumption of Patanjali food products

Sr. No	Media	Consumers	Percentage
1	Television	17	34
2	Social media	15	30
3	Friends	08	16
4	In store promotion	04	08
5	Online advertisement	04	08
6	Patanjali website	02	04

Table 5: Retailers perception of Patanjali food products

Sr. No	Factor	Ranking		
		Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied
		1	2	3
Retailers (n=5)				
1	Level of demand	03 (60)	02 (40)	00 (00)
2	Supply of food product	04 (80)	01 (20)	00 (00)
3	Rate of food product profit margin	02 (40)	03 (60)	00 (00)
4	Profitability	02 (40)	03 (60)	00 (00)
5	Consistency of availability of product	04 (80)	01 (20)	00 (00)

Table 6: Consumer perception of Patanjali food products

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Satisfaction	10 (20)	18 (36)	21 (42)	01 (02)	00 (00)
Will recommend to other	08 (16)	13 (26)	26 (52)	03 (06)	00 (00)
Likely to continue	05 (10)	22 (44)	19 (38)	03 (06)	01 (02)
Some products are costly	12 (24)	15 (30)	17 (34)	02 (04)	04 (08)
Impact of Advertisement	08 (16)	26 (52)	16 (32)	00 (00)	00 (00)
Product have natural ingredients	04 (08)	05 (10)	31 (62)	02 (04)	08 (16)
Patanjali food product is first choice	06 (12)	04 (08)	16 (32)	18 (36)	06 (12)

Table 7: Consumers response on various factor for food product

Factor	Ranking				
	Very satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Very dissatisfied
	1	2	3	4	5
	Consumers				
Price	13 (26)	21 (42)	09 (18)	04 (08)	03 (06)
Taste	26 (52)	11 (22)	09 (18)	02 (04)	02 (04)
Quality	14 (28)	18 (36)	13 (26)	05 (10)	00 (00)
Quantity	31 (62)	14 (28)	05 (10)	00 (00)	00 (00)
Packaging	14 (28)	17 (34)	16 (32)	03 (06)	00 (00)
Effectiveness	25 (50)	14 (28)	08 (16)	03 (06)	00 (00)
Availability	31 (62)	12 (24)	07 (14)	00 (00)	00 (00)
Instruction on Product	15 (30)	18 (36)	13 (26)	01 (02)	00 (00)

Table 8: Constraint faced by consumer and retailer

Factors	Response			
Challenges in finding food product	Frequently	Occasionally	Rarely	Never
	01 (02)	03 (06)	16 (32)	30 (60)
Pricing is affordable compared to another brands	Very affordable	Somewhat affordable	Not very affordable	Not affordable
	07 (14)	23 (46)	17 (34)	03 (06)
Accessible in terms of location	Very accessible	Somewhat accessible	Neutral	Not very accessible
	13 (26)	08 (16)	27 (54)	02 (04)
Find sufficient variety of product	Yes	Not sure	No	
	19 (38)	25 (50)	06 (12)	
Concerns about safety and reliability	Significant concerns	Some concerns	No concerns	
	03 (06)	13 (26)	34 (68)	
Faced any issue with Patanjali food product	Frequently	Occasionally	Never	
	04 (08)	16 (32)	30 (60)	
Brand image affects willingness to purchase	significantly	somewhat	Not at all	
	19 (38)	24 (48)	07 (14)	